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Research Article

Development And Evaluation Of Bilayer Floating Tablet For Helicobacter Pyloric Induced Ulcer Treatment Using Omeprazole And Tinidazole

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ABSTRACT

Development and evaluation of bilayer floating tablet containing ulcer and antibiotic drugs. This study aims to develop a bilayer tablet containing an anti-ulcer and anti-antibiotic combination, with omeprazole as the immediate release layer and tinidazole as the sustained release layer, and to conduct in vitro release studies of the formulation. The combination of these drugs, which have complementary mechanisms of action, is intended to achieve a fixed dose, improve patient compliance, optimize formulation that enhances safety, and increase the therapeutic efficacy of the drugs. Several methods have been developed, including floating drug delivery systems, swelling and expanding systems, bio-adhesive systems, modified form systems, and high-viscosity systems. Locally active medicines, with a short window for immersion in the stomach or upper small intestine, are unstable in the intestinal or colonic region and have low solubility at high pH situations and are particularly interested in floating drug delivery systems. From this discussion it is concluded the bilayer tablet containing Anti-ulcer (Omeprazole) and anti-biotic (Tinidazole) containing bilayer tablet were prepared by using super disintegrating agent for immediate release and hydrophilic mucoadhesive / swellable polymer for achieving sustained release layer are a good means of promising therapy which achieving higher patient compliance.

INTRODUCTION

oral drug delivery is convenient, non-invasive, and has a high patient compliance rate, it continues to be the most popular and preferred method of

medicine administration. The majority of therapy treatments begin with this approach because it is not only the most economical but also the easiest to

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use[1,2].It lowers the frequency of dosage and increases patient adherence[3]. Lipowski, a trailblazing formulation chemist, first presented this idea in the late 1930s[4]. His research paved the way for the development of contemporary sustained-release technologies, which are today essential to oral medication delivery. The limitations of traditional drug delivery techniques, which frequently lead to variable drug levels and related side effects, are intended to be addressed by sustained-release systems[5]. An illustration of this cutting-edge strategy are bilayer pills, which can deliver two distinct medications with separate release profiles. With an emphasis on boosting patient compliance, managing release patterns, and increasing medication bioavailability, oral drug delivery systems have undergone substantial development[5,6].It lowers the frequency of dosage and increases patient adherence. Lipowski, a trailblazing formulation chemist, first presented this idea in the late 1930s[7].His research paved the way for the development of contemporary sustained-release technologies, which are today essential to oral medication delivery. The limitations of traditional drug delivery techniques, which frequently lead to variable drug levels and related side effects, are intended to be addressed by sustained-release systems[8] Tablets are the solid unit dosage forms which containing one or more active pharmaceutical ingredients and additives obtained by compression of uniform volume of particles[9]. The tablets are in the shapes by their formulation spherical, oval, oblong, triangle. The particles present in the tablets which consist of one or more active pharmaceutical ingredient with or without excipients such as diluents, lubricants, glidants, disintegrating agents, gastro intestinal behaviour modifying agents, flavouring and colouring agents. The various tablets are swallow tablets, chewing able Tablet, Mucoadhesive tablets, dispersed or dissolving tablets, sublingual tablets.

Tablets are the unit dosage formulation which offers highest capabilities..Dose precision and very less content variability[10].Packaging and strips are very economical and minimum time required. Suitable for large scale production. Identification is easy..Easy to administration and self-administration is possible. Gastric ulcers are a break in the mucosa of the stomach lining that penetrates through the muscular is mucosa and extends more than 5 mm in diameter. When alterations occur to the defense mechanisms of the stomach, it can cause changes in the gastric mucosa which will eventually result in erosion and then ulceration. This activity reviews the evaluation and management of gastric ulcers and explains the role of the inter professional team in improving care for patients with this condition. Gastric ulcers are a common clinical presentation in the United States and often lead to the expenditure of millions of healthcare dollars. They are a break in the mucosal barrier of the stomach lining that penetrates through the muscularis mucosa and are greater than 5 mm in diameter[9,10]. The body has natural ways to protect the stomach mucosa from the harmful acidic environment that is the gastric lumen. When alterations occur to these defenses, it can lead to changes in the gastric mucosa which will eventually cause erosion and then ulceration. Gastric mucosa protection is via prostaglandins, mucous, growth factors, and adequate blood flow. Known damaging factors of this barrier include smoking, hydrochloric acid, ischemia, NSAID medications, hypoxia, alcohol, and Helicobacter pylori infection. Gastric ulcers are a part of peptic ulcer disease, which carries a lifetime prevalence of 5 to 10% of patients, which is likely an underestimation of the disease as some patients may remain asymptomatic. Studies have shown that the prevalence of gastric ulcers increases with age and with the chronicity of NSAID use[11]. Research shows that smoking leads to a relative

risk of times that of non smokers for developing gastric ulcers. There is no difference between men and women in the prevalence of gastric ulcers. The prevalence of *Helicobacter pylori* infection at age 60 approximates 50% in the US population. Estimates are that 25% of chronic NSAID users will develop gastric ulcers. The pathophysiology of gastric ulcer development depends on the insult. Since about 80 to 90% of gastric ulcers result from either *Helicobacter pylori* and/or NSAID[12]. First, regarding *Helicobacter pylori* these bacteria colonize about 45-50% of the stomach mucosa worldwide. It is a bacterium that people are inoculated with at an early age, especially in developing countries with lower socioeconomic status and crowded households. These bacteria induce an inflammatory response in the host that leads to an epithelial response, degeneration, and injury, known as gastritis[13]. Typically, patients with this infection develop pan gastritis. This damages the antral somatostatin release, which leads to an increase in gastrin secretion, which stimulates increased acid production. Patients who develop gastric ulcers are those in whom the bacteria have remained in the antrum. Parietal cells of the more proximal gastric body still have full production capabilities preventing ulcer genesis in this area. Of note, not all patients with this infection are symptomatic; this depends on the virulence of the bacteria and other host risk factors[14]. A common bacterial virulence factor is the production of cag A, which leads to more cytokine cell destruction and mucosal damage. Antibiotics that disrupt DNA synthesis in anaerobic organisms (*H. pylori*): The 5 nitroimidazoles, metronidazole and tinidazole, were found to bind to the same subset of proteins, including thioredoxin reductase. *E. histolytica* and *T. vaginalis*, none of the other bound proteins in *G. lamblia* are likely candidates for involvement in the thioredoxin mediated redox network. Notably, translation elongation factor EF 1 γ , essential for

protein synthesis, was extensively degraded following treatment with 5 nitroimidazoles. All tested nitroimidazoles reduced intracellular thiol pools in *G. lamblia*, but metronidazole had the least effect, differing significantly from its impact on the other two parasites. This indicates that nitroimidazole drugs affect *G. lamblia* in a fundamentally different manner than they do *E. histolytica* and *T. vaginalis*. The selective toxicity of 5 nitroimidazoles to microaerophiles and anaerobes is thought to be due to the presence of factors in these organisms that can transfer electrons to the nitro group, thereby activating the prodrug metronidazole to its active form. Tinidazole is a prodrug and antiprotozoal agent. The nitro group of tinidazole is reduced in *Trichomonas* by a ferredoxin mediated electron transport system. The free nitro radical generated as a result of this reduction is believed to be responsible for the antiprotozoal activity. It is suggested that the toxic free radicals covalently bind to DNA, causing DNA damage and leading to cell death. The mechanism by which tinidazole exhibits activity against *Giardia* and *Entamoeba* species is not known, though it is probably similar. For the treatment of the trichomoniasis caused by *T. vaginalis* in both female and male patients. Also for the treatment of giardiasis caused by *G. duodenalis* in both adults and pediatric patients older than three years of age and for the treatment of intestinal amebiasis and amebic liver abscess caused by the *E. histolytica* in both adults and pediatric patients older than three years of age. Omeprazole is heavily metabolized in the liver by the cytochrome P450 (CYP) enzyme system. The main part of its metabolism depends on the polymorphically expressed CYP2C19, which is responsible for the formation of hydroxyomeprazole, the major metabolite found in plasma. The remaining part depends on CYP3A4, responsible for the formation of the omeprazole

sulphone. Omeprazole, according to the FDA label is a proton pump inhibitor (PPI) used for the following purposes: Treatment of active duodenal ulcer in adults. Eradication of *Helicobacter pylori* to reduce the risk of duodenal ulcer recurrence in adults. Treatment of active benign gastric ulcer in adults . Reduction of risk of upper gastrointestinal (GI) bleeding in critically ill adult patients. Treatment of symptomatic gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) in patients 1 year of age and older. Treatment of erosive esophagitis (EE) due to acid mediated GERD in patients 1 month of age and older. Maintenance of healing of due to acid mediated GERD in patients 1 year of age and older. pathologic hypersecretory conditions in adults

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Omeprazole and Tinidazole purchased from Sigma Aldrich, Micro crystalline cellulose and starch purchased from Nice chemicals, Magnesium stearate, Sodium starch glycolate, Quinolin yellow, Talc purchased from LOBA chemie

PREFORMULATION STUDIES[15]

As a starting point to developing dosage forms, various physical and chemical properties of the drug substance need to be documented. These investigations are termed preformulation studies. In the rational development of dosage form Preformulation studies are the important and initial step. The aim of preformulation study is to develop information about the drug substances, so that this information would be useful to develop a formulation. It is an essential study for physical and chemical properties of a drug substances alone and in combination with excipients. Preformulation investigation is designed to identify the physiochemical properties of drugs and excipients that may influence the formulation design, method of formulation pharmacokinetic and biopharmaceutical properties of the resulting product. These studies are performed for the preformulation investigation.

Melting point:

The powdered drug is placed into a capillary tube, which is then sealed at one end. The capillary tube should be 6 7 cm in length and 1 mm in diameter, with the drug standing 3 4 mm from the bottom. The tube is moistened with a liquid from the bath and positioned in an iron stand attached to a thermometer. Adjust the setup so that the drug in the capillary is aligned with the middle of the thermometer's mercury bulb. The thermometer is then lowered into a beaker filled with paraffin oil. The beaker is heated slowly while maintaining a uniform temperature with constant stirring. Once the drug in the capillary starts to show signs of melting, remove the burner while continuing to stir. Record the temperature at which the drug fully melts and becomes transparent.

Preparation of Buffer Solutions:

1. Phosphate Buffer (pH 7.4):

Dissolve 8.40 grams of sodium dihydrogen phosphate (NaH_2PO_4) and 15.62 grams of disodium hydrogen phosphate (Na_2HPO_4) in 1000 ml of water. Stir until fully dissolved.

2. Acidic Buffer (0.1N HCl):

Pipette 8.34 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid (HCl) into a 1 liter volumetric flask. Dilute with distilled water up to 1000 ml and Mix thoroughly to ensure even distribution.

Formulation Trials:

To develop an optimized bilayer tablet formulation, several trials were conducted. The general procedures for each layer in all formulation trials are outlined below.\

Formulation Procedure for Layer 1:

Dispensing:

Dispense the materials required for the first layer into separate poly bags to keep them organized and ready for the next steps.

Sifting:

Pass the materials through selected sieves to achieve a uniform particle size and ensure better mixing.

Formulation Procedure for Layer I:

1. Dry Mixing:

In a mortar, mix the API with microcrystalline cellulose, lactose monohydrate, and sodium starch glycolate for approximately 10 minutes until thoroughly blended.

2. Binder Solution:

Prepare the binder solution by mixing starch with a sufficient amount of purified water to enhance the mechanical strength of the formulation layer.

3. Granulation:

Add the prepared binder solution to the dry mixed materials. Mix thoroughly to ensure uniform distribution and pass the mixture through a #60 sieve.

4. Drying:

Load the granulated blend into a rapid dryer and dry it at an internal temperature of 50°C with an airflow rate of 50 until the loss on drying falls within the range of 1.5% to 2.5%.

5. Lubrication:

Add talc and magnesium stearate to the dried blend to improve its flow properties.

Formulation Procedure for Layer II:

Dispensing:

Dispense the materials required for the second layer into separate poly bags and prepare them for the next steps.

Sifting:

Pass the materials through a series of specified mesh sizes to achieve uniform particle size and ensure effective mixing.

Formulation Procedure for Layer II:

1. Dispensing:

Dispense the materials required for the second layer into separate poly bags and prepare them for processing.

2. Sifting:

Sift the materials through a series of specified mesh sizes to ensure uniform particle size and effective mixing.

3. Binder Solution:

Prepare the binder solution by mixing starch with an adequate amount of purified water to enhance the mechanical strength of the formulation.

4. Dry Mixing:

Mix the API II with microcrystalline cellulose and Tartrazine yellow in a mortar for approximately 10 minutes until thoroughly combined.

5. Granulation:

Add the prepared binder solution to the dry mixed materials and mix thoroughly. Pass the mixture through a #60 mesh sieve.

6. Drying:

Load the granulated blend into a rapid dryer and dry at an internal temperature of 50°C with an airflow rate of 50 until the loss on drying falls within the range of 1.5% to 2.5%.

7. Sifting:

Sift the dried blend through a #20 mesh size. Retain the granules and mill them, then pass the blend through a #20 mesh again before pre lubrication.

8. Pre Lubrication:

Sift guar gum polymer and set it aside. Add it to the blend and mix for 20 minutes.

9. Lubrication:

Add talc and magnesium stearate to the pre lubricated blend to improve its flow properties.

Pre compression parameters: (M.Sunitha reddy et al.,2018) The formulated blends have undergone following preformulation studies,

- Bulk density
- Angle of repose
- Carr's compressibility studies
- FT-IR studies
- Hausner's ratio

Bulk density (Db):

The bulk density depends on the particle size distribution, cohesiveness and shape of the particles. 10gm powder is accurately weighted and poured in to a graduated measuring cylinder through a funnel and shaken without tapping, the

volume which is measured is called initial bulk. Bulk density is expressed in gm/cc is given by,

$$\text{Bulk density (D b)} = \frac{\text{Mass of the powder(gm)}}{\text{Bulk volume of powder(cc)}}$$

Bulk volume of powder(cc)

Tapped density (Dt):

10gm of powder is taken for the determination of bulk density is dropped from the particular height in to a measuring cylinder. The cylinder is tapped constantly until there is no change in the volume of the powder and tapped volume was read. The tapped volume is expressed in gm/cc is given by,

$$\text{Tapped density (D t)} = \frac{\text{Mass of the powder(gm)}}{\text{Tapped volume of powder(cc)}}$$

Tapped volume of powder(cc)

Angle of repose (θ):

The fractional force in a loose powder can be determined by the angle of repose. This is the maximum angle possible between the surface of pile of powder and the horizontal plane. The

Limits of pre compression parameters :

Table 10. Limits of pre compression parameters

Flow character	Carr's index	Hausner's ratio	Angle of repose
Excellent	<10	1.00-1.11	25-30
Good	11-15	1.12-1.18	31-35
Fair (aid not needed)	16-20	1.19-1.25	36-40
Passable (May hangup)	21-25	1.26-1.34	41-45
Poor (vibrate)	26-31	1.35-1.45	46-55
Very poor	32-37	1.46-1.59	56-65
Very, very poor	>38	>1.60	>66

Formulation chart for each formulation trials (F1- F7)

Table 11. Formulation chart for each formulation trials

Ingredients	IRLF1	IRLF2	IRLF3	IRLF4
Omeprazole	20	20	20	20
Sodium Starch Glycolate	10	20	25	30
Lactose	105	105	110	115
Micro Crystalline Cellulose	120	110	100	90
Magnesium Stearate	3	3	3	3
Talc	2	2	2	2
Ingredients	SRLF1	SRLF2	SRLF3	SRLF4
Tinidazole	500	500	500	500
Guar gum	50	100	125	150
Lactose	195	145	120	95
Magnesium stearate	3	3	3	3
Talc	2	2	2	2

powder is allowed to fall through the fixed funnel in a definite height. Angle of repose is calculated by measuring the height and radius of the heap of powder produced

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} (h / r)$$

Carr's index(CI)

The percentage compressibility of powder is direct measurement of the potential powder arch or the bridge strength and stability. Carr's index of each formulation was calculated by the equation given below,

$$\text{CI} = \frac{\text{Df} - \text{Do}}{\text{D}} \times 100$$

Where, Df = tapped density,

D0 = bulk density

Hausner's ratio(IH):

Is calculated from the df and do using the following expression

$$\text{Hausner's ratio (IH)} = \frac{\text{tapped density}}{\text{bulk density}}$$

Tartrazine yellow	Q.s	Q.s	Q.s	Q.s
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POST COMPRESSION PARAMETERS

Thickness and diameter:

The thickness and diameter of tablets will result in uniform size and shape of the tablets. This may improve the patient compliance, the tablet thickness was measured in mm by using Vernier calibre.

Hardness:

The mechanical strength of the tablets was performed by the hardness test. The tablets hardness is measured by the pressure applied on tablet to form a crack along its axis. It is tested by using the Monsanto hardness tester. The tablet was held between a fixed and moving jaw scale was adjusted to zero, pressure was gradually increased until the tablet fractured. The value of the pressure applied to break the tablet is noted. The tablets were randomly picked and hardness of the tablets was determined.

1N =22.4 Kg/cm²

Friability:

The tablet strength was tested by using the TECH-NU friabilator. 20 tablets were weighed and placed in a friability apparatus. Operate to set the rpm 100 for 4 min, after that take the tablets and reweigh it. 1% of tablet friability is generally acceptable. The percentage weight loss can be determined by using the following formula. Twenty tablets are selected randomly, individually weighted in a single pan electronic balance and the average weight was calculated. The uniformity of weight was determined according to IP specification. From the standard value in IP, not more than two of individual weight should deviate from average weight by more than 5% and none deviate more than twice that percentage.

Table 12. Weight variation limit

S No	Average weight of tablets	% of deviation
1	≤ 80mg	±10
2	80mg < 250mg	±7.5
3	≥ 250mg	±5

Drug content analysis:

The uniformity of the drug in each formulated tablets were determined by this assay. The tablets are randomly selected, weighed and crushed. The following assay procedure is performed to determine the drug content in UV spectroscopy API-I (Omeprazole) at 276 nm and API-II (Tinidazole) at 280 nm against blank. The contents of drug in the formulated bilayer tablets were determined by using the UV spectroscopy.

Data analysis

The data obtained from the dissolution study was subjected to the analysis to know the release pattern of the drug from the dosage form to analyze the mechanism of release and release rate kinetic

of the dosage form and the data obtained were fitted into,

- Zero order
- First order kinetics
- Higuchi model kinetic
- Korsmeyer-peppas model

Based on the r²- value, the best-fit model was selected.

Zero order kinetics

It describes the system in which the drug release rate is independent of its concentration.

$$Q_t = Q_0 + K_0 t$$

Where,

Q_t = amount of drug dissolved in time t.

Q_0 = initial amount of the drug in the solution and the K_0 = zero order release constant.

If the drug release obeys zero order release kinetics, the plot of percentage drug release vs time will give a straight line with a slope of k_0 and intercept at zero.

First order kinetics

It describes the system in which the drug release rate dependent of its concentration.

$$\log Q_t = \log Q_0 + kt / 2.303$$

Where,

Q_t = amount of drug dissolved in time t .

Q_0 = initial amount of the drug in the solution K_t = is the first order release constant.

If the drug release obeys the first order drug release kinetics, then the plot of log percentage drug remaining to be released vs time, shown a straight line with a slope of $kt / 2.303$ and an intercept at $t=0$ of $\log Q_0$

Higuchi model

It defines the fraction of drug release from the matrix is proportional to square root of time.

Where,

$$M_t / M_\infty = kHt^{1/2}$$

M_t/M_∞ = cumulative amount, if drug release from at time t and infinite time. kH = Higuchi dissolution constant and reflection formulation characteristics k' is the release constant, t' is the release time.

If the drug release obeys higuchi model, plot of cumulative percentage drug release vs

$t^{1/2}$ will be straight line with the slop of kH

Korsmeyer-peppas model

The power law describes the drug released from the polymeric system in which the release deviates from the fickian diffusion, which is expressed in following equation,

$$\log [M_t - M_\infty] = \log k + n \log t$$

where,

$M_t - M_\infty$ = cumulative amount of drug release at the time t and infinite time

k = constant incorporating structure and geometrical characteristic of CR device.

n = diffusion release exponent indicative of mechanism of drug release for the drug dissolution.

A plot of $\log [M_t - M_\infty]$ (log % drug release) vs log time (log t) will be linear with slope of n and intercept gives the value of $\log k$. antilog of k gives the value of k .

Swelling study:

The extent swelling study is measured in terms of percentage weight gain of tablets. The optimized formulation was determined in 900ml of 0.1 N HCl solution (pH 1.2), at 37°C

± 0.50 °C. and the swelled tablets are weighted time respectively 1 to 12 hrs ,the excess of fluid was removed by using absorbing paper, the tablets were weighted and the swelling index can be calculating by using the formula

$$SI = \frac{M_t - M_0}{M_0} \times 100$$

Where,

SI = swelling index

M_t = weight of tablet at time t M_0 = weight of tablet at time

FT-IR studies

Interaction between the drug and polymer was studied by IR spectroscopy using the FT-IR spectrometer (460 plus, jasco-Japan) with diffuse reflectance principle. By Potassium bromide pellet technique, sample is triturated in glass motor and finally placed in the sample holder. The spectrum was scanned over the frequency range of 4000-400 cm^{-1} .

Stability studies:

Stability studies were carried out at 40°C $\pm$ 2°C / 75% of RH $\pm$ 5% RH for 30 days, for the selected formulation. The stability studies were done for formulation. These formulations were selected depending upon the in vitro drug release study of both drugs from both layers of the tablets. The formulations were subjected to stability study.

Table 14. Stability studies

Formulation	Stability criteria	Frequency (Days)	Tests
Formulation (SRL/IRL F1-F4)	40 ⁰ c ± 2 ⁰ c / 75% ofRH ± 5% RH	Upto 30 days	Physical observation
			Uniformity of drugcontent and, in-vitro drug release.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preformulation studies:

Determination of Melting point:

The melting point of Omeprazole was found to be 1560c. which was closer to the melting point of

UV spectra of Omeprazole:

Omeprazole. The melting point of Tinidazole was found to be 1260c. This was closer to the melting point of Tinidazole.

UV spectra of Omeprazole

UV spectra of Tinidazole:

UV spectra of Tinidazole

Calibration curve:

Standard graph of Omeprazole in 0.1N Hcl.

The standard curve was prepared by plotting absorbance against the concentration of individual analyzed value. The calibration graph was

obtained (R2=0.995) in the concentration range of 5 to 30 µg/ml.

Calibration curve of Omeprazole:

Table 15. Calibration curve of Omeprazole

S No	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance at 276 nm
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1.	0	0
2.	5	0.169
3.	10	0.347
4.	15	0.51
5.	20	0.643
6.	25	0.826
7.	30	0.919

Physical compatibility study:

S No	Drug + Excipients	Description and condition			
		INITIAL	Room temperature 40°C /75% of RH in days		
			10Days	20Days	30Days
1	Tinidazole	White color crystalline solid	NC	NC	NC
2	Omeprazole	White color	NC	NC	NC
3	Tinidazole + Omeprazole	White color powder	NC	NC	NC
4	Tinidazole + Guar gum	Yellowish white	NC	NC	NC
5	Omeprazole + SSG	White color powder	NC	NC	NC
6	Tinidazole + MCC	White color crystalline powder	NC	NC	NC
7	Tinidazole + Omeprazole + MCC + SSG	White color powder	NC	NC	NC
8	Tinidazole + MCC + SSG	White color powder	NC	NC	NC
9	Omeprazole + MCC + SSG	White color powder	NC	NC	NC
10	Tinidazole + Talc + Magnesium stearate	White color powder	NC	NC	NC
11	Omeprazole + talc + Magnesium stearate	White color powder	NC	NC	NC
12	Omeprazole + guar gum	Yellowish white	NC	NC	NC

NC – No Change

Table 17. Physical compatibility study

Pre formulation studies of formulated Granules: The formulated granules (layer I) using sodium starch glycolate (IRL 1-IRL 4) and the formulated

(layer II), using the guar gum (SRL1-SRL 4) were subjected to preformulation tests and the results were given in table.

Table 18. Pre formulation studies of formulated Granules

Evaluation of pre compression layer I granules (IRL FI- IRL F4)					
LAYER – I	Angle of repose (θ)	Bulk density	True density (gm/cc)	Carr's index (gm/cc)	Hausner's Ratio
IRL F1	25 ⁰ 82'	0.448	0.509	11.98428291	1.136160714
IRL F3	28 ⁰ 91'	0.481	0.547	12.06581353	1.137214137
IRL F5	34 ⁰ 35'	0.571	0.642	11.05919003	1.124343257
IRL F7	43 ⁰ 37'	0.602	0.675	10.81481481	1.121262458
Evaluation of pre compression layer II granules (SRL F1-SRL F4)					
SRL F1	27 ⁰ 12'	0.352	0.412	14.5631068	1.170454545
SRL F3	28 ⁰ 89'	0.331	0.383	13.5770235	1.157099698
SRL F5	20 ⁰ 90'	0.351	0.396	11.36363636	1.128205128
SRL F7	36 ⁰ 42'	0.343	0.393	12.72264631	1.145772595

Compression of bilayer tablets:

Compression of bilayer tablets involves forming a single tablet by compressing two distinct layers with different properties. This technique is essential for combining drugs with varied release profiles, separating incompatible substances, or achieving dual-action effects. It requires specialized equipment to ensure proper layer adhesion and uniform compression, preventing issues like separation or inconsistent drug release. Formulation Considerations include layer compatibility, appropriate compression force, strong adhesion, and rigorous quality control to ensure tablet integrity and effectiveness, making this method crucial for controlled-release and combination therapies.

Fig 20. Formulated Bilayer tablets

POST COMPRESSION PARAMETER OF BILAYER TABLETS:

Physical parameters:

The post compression parameters were performed in the formulated bilayer tablet and the results were summarized below. All the formulation complies within the standard limits. From this resulted data formulated bilayer tablets have a hardness range of 5.4 - 5.6 respectively, Hardness of the tablets depends the ratio of polymers and

excipients used. The friability of each formulation is below 1%, which complies with the standard limits.

Table 19. Post compression parameter of bilayer tablets

Formulation	Weight variation(mg)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Thickness (mm)	Friability (%)	Drug content (%)	
					API-I	API-II
LT F1	556 ± 2	5.1	5.6	0.926	97.5	98.4
LT F2	551 ± 3	4.9	5.5	0.913	97.6	98.2
LT F3	556 ± 2	5.6	5.5	0.943	96.2	97.8

Swelling study:

The swelling studies were performed in the formulated bilayer tablet (SRL F1- SRL F4) and the results were summarized below. The formulations (SRL F1- SRL F2) which have the

higher swelling index results in minimizing the time of drug release from the formulated bilayer tablet, and the formulation SRL F3 & SRL F4 have similar range of swelling index with optimized polymer ratio.

Fig 21. Swelling study of sustained release layer (SRL F1- SRL F4)

Swelling index (SI):

Time in hours	SRL F1	SRL F2	SRL F3	SRL F4
0	0	0	0	0
1	2	5	7	10
2	13	20	27	37
3	26	41	53	69
4	39	63	74	91
5	48	78	99	119
6	60	88	121	142
7	73	103	137	179
8	85	126	154	193
9	99	143	181	216
10	116	165	217	241
11	135	187	235	274
12	155	200	252	295

Comparison of In-vitro dissolution profiles of all formulation:

Layer II drug release profile (%)				
Dissolution Medium	pH 7.4 phosphate buffer solution			
Formulation	SRL F1	SRL F2	SRL F3	SRL F4
1 Hrs	18.38	14.11	7.31	5.47
2 Hrs	26.65	19.48	12.89	8.11
3 Hrs	37.90	27.90	18.58	14.34
4 Hrs	43.59	33.07	25.66	19.93
5 Hrs	57.68	42.59	33.65	23.50
6 Hrs	69.25	51.54	39.62	29.75
7 Hrs	80.19	61.17	46.83	36.15
8 Hrs	98.23	72.29	52.75	39.38
9 Hrs		83.59	61.4	49.63
10 Hrs		94.54	69.38	57.36
11Hs			79.95	69.36
12Hrs			86.99	73.85

Layer I drug release profile (%)				
DissolutionMedium	0.1 N Hcl Solution			
Formulation	IRL F1	IRL F2	IRL F3	IRL F4
10 min	8.96	17.56	21.37	25.027
20 min	26.43	25.4	32.079	42.33
30 min	32.83	34.43	40.93	70.71
40 min	47.18	44.18	52.45	96.60
50 min	56.33	70.77	77.07	
60 min	64.12	78.73	98.85	

Table 21. In-vitro dissolution profiles of formulation

In-vitro dissolution drug release data discussion:

LAYER I:

The formulation IRL F1 formulated by using (1:0.5) SSG which produced 64.12 % of drug release at the end of 60 min. The drug release was gradually increased with increase in concentration of SSG as observed from IRL F1 to IRL F4. Among these all formulations the tablet IRL F3 composed SSG (1:2.5) shows the better drug release rate (98.85%) at the end of 60 min.

LAYER II:

The drug polymer ratio 1: 0.5(SRL F1) shows the drug release (98.23% at the end of 8 hrs) due to the low concentration of guar gum. The formulation (SRL F4) shows the drug release (73.85% at the end of 12 hrs) with the higher concentration of polymer ratio (1:3.5). From the release, the rate of drug release is very low at the higher concentration of polymer. optimized swelling index of the polymer favours the sustained release in dissolution of the drug. The formulation (SRL F2

ratio 1:1.5) shows the drug release rate above 90% at the end of 10 hours. The polymer guar gum is well known strong viscous gel in contact with aqueous media to retard the drug release by swelling which may be useful in the sustained delivery of drug.

Hence the formulation SRL F3 (ratio1:2.5) shows above 85% of drug release at the end of 12 hours, which was selected as a best formula and considered optimum for stability studies. In the formulation SRL F3 all the specified parameters are within the limit. This dissolution profile was taken for kinetic modelling studies.

Mathematical analysis of in-vitro release data:

The in-vitro data is applied in the various kinetic models to predict the drug release mechanism. The slope values and the regression coefficient are summarized in the table. The correlation coefficient is in the range of 0.986 – 0.996. It was found that the drug release data of the formulation batches are good fit to the zero order and the Korsmeyer Peppas equation.

Time in Hrs	Log time	Sq root of time	Cumulative Drug release	Log cumulative Drug release
0	0	0	0	0
1	0	1	0.832395046	0.079670513
2	0.30103	1.414213562	1.745335371	0.24187889

3	0.47712	1.732050808	2.261187068	0.354336493
4	0.60206	2	3.508669776	0.545142496
5	0.69897	2.236067977	4.192954801	0.622520181
6	0.77815	2.449489743	4.986569085	0.69780184
7	0.8451	2.645751311	5.549437028	0.744248928
8	0.90309	2.828427125	6.120162458	0.786762951
9	0.95424	3	7.234381535	0.859401409
10	1	3.16227766	8.653836255	0.937208673
11	1.04139	3.31662479	9.314846389	0.969175697
12	1.07918	3.464101615	9.99105678	0.999611427

Higuchi model

Formulation	Zero order kinetics		First order kinetics		Higuchi's kinetics		Korsmeyer-Peppas kinetics	
	Slope	R ²	Slope	R ²	Slope	R ²	Slope	R ²
SRL F3	9.924	0.986	-0.097	0.993	10.11	0.920	33.623	0.999

Stability studies:

Stability studies were done for the optimized formulation (SRL F3) at $400c \pm 20c$ / , 75% of RH

$\pm 5\%$ RH as per the standard guidelines and the results are summarized in the table.

Table 22. Stability studies

Parameters		Time	10days	20days	30 days
<i>In-vitro</i> drug release(%)	API I	20 min	94.65	94.61	92.9
		2hour	8.83	9.03	9.10
	API II	6hour	40.81	40.98	42.12
		10hour	71.59	71.59	71.64
		12hour	98.10	98.06	98.15

Stability studies were done for the optimized formulation (PF4) at $400c \pm 20c$, 75% of RH $\pm 5\%$ RH as per the standard guidelines and there is no significant change in the drug content and the drug release from the optimized formulation (SRL F3).

FT-IR Analysis data:

Sample Preparation: Omeprazole can be prepared for FT-IR analysis in a solid form, often by mixing with potassium bromide (KBr) to form a pellet or by applying it as a thin film. The FT- IR spectrum typically ranges from 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} . In this range, the functional groups in Omeprazole absorb specific wavelengths of infrared light, resulting in characteristic peaks. O-H and N-H Stretching: Peaks in the range of 3400-3200 cm^{-1} correspond to O-H and N-H stretching vibrations, which can indicate the presence of hydroxyl or amine groups. C=O Stretching: A strong peak around 1700 cm^{-1} suggests the presence of carbonyl groups. C-N and C-O Stretching: Peaks in the range of 1300-1000

cm^{-1} are associated with C-N and C-O stretching vibrations, which are relevant for identifying the benzimidazole ring structure in Omeprazole. Aromatic Ring: Peaks around 1600 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of an aromatic ring, which is part of the benzimidazole moiety in Omeprazole. Characteristic Peaks in the FT- IR Sample of Tinidazole using KBr pellet technique: O-H and N-H Stretching (3400-3200 cm^{-1}): These peaks are associated with hydroxyl and amine groups. C-H Stretching (3100-3000 cm^{-1}): Indicates the presence of aromatic C-H bonds, related to the aromatic ring in the Tinidazole structure. C=O Stretching (1700-1650 cm^{-1}): A strong peak in this region suggests the presence of carbonyl groups. C=N Stretching (1600-1500 cm^{-1}): Associated with the imidazole ring, indicating the presence of a nitrogen double bond. N-O Stretching (1400-1300 cm^{-1}): This peak is characteristic of the nitro group, a key functional group in Tinidazole. C-N

and C-O Stretching ($1300-1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$): Reflects the vibrations within the imidazole ring and ether linkages. Aromatic C-H Bending ($900-700\text{ cm}^{-1}$): Peaks in this range are related out-of-plane bending vibrations

Table 23. FT-IR Analysis data

S. No	Peaks in the range of wave number (cm^{-1})	Mode of vibration	Functional group
PHYSICAL MIXTURE (OMEPRAZOLE + TINIDAZOLE + EXCIPIENTS)			
1.	$3400-3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$	O-H and N-H stretching vibrations	Hydroxyl or amine groups
2.	$3100-3000$	C-H Stretching (Aromatic)	Aromatic ring vibrations
3.	1700 cm^{-1}	Strong peak	Carbonyl groups
4.	$1300-1000\text{ cm}^{-1}$	C-N and C-O Stretching	Benzimidazole ring structure
5.	1600 cm^{-1}	Peak identified	Aromatic Ring
6.	$900-700$	Out-of-plane bending (C-H)	Aromatic C-H bending
7.	$1600-1500$	C=N Stretching	Nitrogen double bond in the imidazole ring
8.	$1400-1300$	N-O Stretching	Nitro group characteristic of Tinidazole
9.	$1300-1000$	C-N and C-O Stretching	Imidazole ring and ether linkages

Fig 22. FTIR Spectra of Tinidazole

Fig 23. FTIR Spectra of Omeprazole

CONCLUSION:

Omeprazole is used to treat excess stomach acid in conditions stomach ulcers, gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD), active duodenal ulcer, Zollinger-Ellison syndrome and erosive esophagitis. Omeprazole may prescribe together with antibiotics to treat gastric ulcer caused by infection with *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*). Tinidazole is a nitro imidazole antimicrobial agent. It is effective against protozoa and anaerobic organisms, including *H. pylori*. Anti-ulcer (Omeprazole) and anti-biotic (Tinidazole) containing bilayer tablet were prepared by using super disintegrating agent for immediate release and hydrophilic mucoadhesive / swellable polymer for achieving sustained release. The formulated bilayer tablets were validated in terms of thickness, hardness, weight variation, friability, drug content, swelling index, in-vitro drug release study, stability study and FT-IR studies. All the formulations were shown fairly acceptable data for all the parameters evaluated for the quality control test for bilayer tablets. The quality control tests to assess the physiochemical properties and release characteristics of all formulations. The release of API from the layer I exhibited that the super disintegrate plays a good role in the disintegration process. In the formulated layer II, the formulations SRL4 have a higher ratio of polymer which results in percentage of drug release below

80 % at the end of 12 hours and the formulation SRL1 & SRL2 shows the percentage drug release above 80% at the end of 8 hours. The formulation SRL 3 has achieved above 80% of drug release at the end of 12 hours. The polymer ability to retard the drug release rate is related to swelling index. The swelling ability and the muco adhesiveness of the guar gum in the aqueous medium. The formulation SRL 3 complies with all the release limits and giving 86.99% at the end of 12 hours, Hence the SRL 3 is considered as best formulae. In the formulation SRL 3 containing guar gum was found to release the drug in sustained manner up to 12 hours is considered for optimum stability studies. From the various kinetic model for sustained release layer, it can be concluded that the srl 3 showing Korsmeyer Peppas kinetic as the plot of the model shown higher regression ($R^2=0.995$). The release mechanism can be concluded that diffusion controlled mechanism. From the results of stability data provided, it can be concluded that the formulation was stable at the condition 40°C /75 % RH for one month. All the parameters like drug content of the tablet and consistency in dissolution studies even after simulating extreme consistency during their storage. From this discussion it is concluded the bilayer tablet containing Anti-ulcer (Omeprazole) and anti-biotic (Tinidazole) containing bilayer tablet were prepared by using super disintegrating agent for

immediate release and hydrophilic mucoadhesive /swellable polymer for achieving sustained release layer are a good means of promising therapy which achieving higher patient compliance.

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